

Increase in Renyi and Shannon Entropies for Increasing Lambda for a Poisson Distribution Using an Infinitesimal Approach

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In (1) it is proved that Renyi and Shannon entropies increase with an increase in the parameter Lambda (called b here) of a Poisson distribution: $p(k) = b^k / k! \exp(-b)$, where k ranges from 0 to infinite. We try to provide an alternative proof here by considering b and $b+\delta$ values, where $\delta > 0$ so that $p(b+\delta) \approx \{1 + \delta(-1+k/b)\}$. Our goal is to show that: $\text{Entropy}(b+\delta) = \text{Entropy}(b) + \delta \text{Number} > \text{Entropy}(b)$.

We apply this infinitesimal comparison approach to both the Shannon and Renyi cases, and also to Tsallis entropy, to show that entropy increases in all cases with an increase in b .

Approach of (1)

In (1), a proof based on the derivatives of entropy is used to show that the Shannon entropy for a Poisson distribution increases with increasing lambda, represented by b here. The Poisson distribution is:

$$p(k) = b^k / k! \exp(-b) \quad ((1))$$

A different proof is applied to Renyi entropy to show that it also increases with increasing lambda (b).

We try to present an alternative proof based on considering the change of b to $b+\delta$, where $0 < \delta \ll 1$.

Infinitesimal Change to Lambda (b) of a Poisson Distribution

We use: $b \rightarrow b + \delta$, where $0 < \delta \ll 1$, which yields:

$$p(k) \rightarrow (b+\delta)^k / k! \exp(-b-\delta) \rightarrow p(k) \{ 1 + \delta(-1+k/b) \} \quad ((2))$$

One may see that: $\sum_k p(k, b+\delta) = \sum_k p(k) = 1$ because $\sum_k k p(k) = b$.

We suggest that the infinitesimal change in b approach may be used for any type of entropy by seeing how δ changes the entropy as $b \rightarrow b + \delta$. We apply this to the Shannon, Renyi and Tsallis cases.

Shannon Entropy

Shannon's entropy is given by: $-\sum_i p_i \ln(p_i) = \text{positive number} \quad ((3))$

because $p_i < 1$ and $\ln(p_i) < 0$.

We consider: $p(k) \{ 1 + \delta (-1+k/b) \}$ where k is the Poisson k label. Then:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\text{Sum over } k \{1+\delta(-1+k/b)\} p(k) \{\ln(p(k)) + \ln(1-\delta(-1+k/b))\} \\
 = & -\text{Sum over } k p(k) \ln(p(k)) + \delta \text{Sum over } k p(k) \ln(p(k)) - \delta/b \text{Sum over } k k p(k) \ln(p(k)) \\
 & + \text{Sum over } k (1+\delta(-1+k/b)) p(k) \delta (-1+k/b) \quad ((4))
 \end{aligned}$$

The last term of ((4)) is 0 because it is equal to (keeping first order in δ):

$$\text{Sum over } k p(k) \delta (-1+k/b) = -\delta + \delta b/b = 0$$

The first term of ((4)) is positive, the second term is negative and multiplied by the tiny δ . Thus, one must consider:

$$-\delta/b \text{Sum over } k k p(k) \ln(p(k)) \quad ((5))$$

Now $\text{Sum over } k k p(k) = b$ and $|k \ln(p(k))| > k$ so $k \ln(p(k)) = -k + \text{function}(k)$ where $\text{function}(k) > 0$. Thus:

$$\delta \text{Sum over } k p(k) \ln(p(k)) - \delta/b \text{Sum over } k k p(k) \ln(p(k)) > 0$$

Thus, one has: Shannon entropy($b+\delta$) = Shannon's entropy (b) + δ (positive number) ((6)) meaning that Shannon's entropy increases with increasing b .

Renyi Entropy

$$\text{Renyi entropy is given by: } 1/(1-q) \ln \{ \text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q \} \quad ((7))$$

Given that $\text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q < 1$, $\ln \{ \text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q \} < 0$, but $1-q < 0$ for $q > 1$ so Renyi entropy is positive.

We next consider:

$$\ln \{ \text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q \{ 1 + \delta (-1+k/b) \} \text{ power } q \} \quad ((8))$$

$$= \ln \{ \text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q \} + q \delta \{ \text{Sum over } k (-1+k/b) p(k) \text{ power } q \} / \{ \text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q \}$$

$$\text{Sum over } k p(k) \text{ power } q > 0$$

Now for $\delta > 0$, $q > 0$ $\text{Sum over } k p(k) = b$, but $k p(k) \text{ power } q < k p(k)$ so:

Sum over k $p(k)$ power $q < b$. So $\{\text{Sum over k } (-1+k/b) p(k) \text{ power } q\} < 0$ ((8))

If $q > 1$, $1/(1-q) < 0$, thus ((7)) is a positive number.

Then: the expression ((8)) / $(1-q) > 0$ and so entropy increases.

Tsallis Entropy

Tsallis entropy = $1/(q-1) \{1 - \text{Sum over k } p(k) \text{ power } q\}$ ((9))

Sum over k $p(k)$ power $q < 1$ so for $q > 1$ Tsallis entropy is positive.

Using ((2)):

Tsallis entropy($b + \delta$) = Tsallis entropy(b) - $1/(q-1) \text{ Sum over k } \delta \alpha (-1+k/b) p(k) \text{ power } q$ ((10))

Now Sum over k $\delta \alpha (-1+k/b) p(k) \text{ power } q < 0$ as shown in the section on Renyi entropy so:

Tsallis entropy($b + \delta$) = Tsallis entropy(b) + positive number * δ ((11))

Thus, for $\delta > 0$, Tsallis entropy increases with increasing b .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider a Poisson distribution with a lambda parameter, which we call b , and focus on $b \rightarrow b + \delta$. This allows one to write: $p(k, b + \delta) \approx p(k) \{1 + \delta(-1+k/b)\}$. Thus, one may easily calculate Entropy($b + \delta$) in terms of Entropy(b) to see if entropy increases with $\delta > 0$, where $\delta \ll 1$. We apply this approach to Shannon, Renyi and Tsallis entropies and show that in all cases entropy increases with increasing b .

References

1. Braiman, V. et al Properties of Shannon and Renyi Entropies of the Poisson Distribution as the functions of the intensity parameter (March 2024)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2403.08805>